

A STATISTICAL STUDY ON RESORTING TO DANGEROUS COSMETIC SURGERIES

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Abstract: The results we obtained from the factor test using Chi-square (χ^2) show the following: -

1. There are cases of death resulting from cosmetic surgeries.
2. Bullying has a societal role in pressuring towards cosmetic surgeries at a rate of 44%.
3. Married women and women over 30 years of age are the most likely to resort to cosmetic surgeries.
4. Setting controls to limit dangerous cosmetic surgeries and tightening legal oversight by the government on the cosmetic industry to protect the consumer is very important and plays an effective role in reducing the occurrence of risks.
5. Good financial status and external appearance have a direct impact on self-confidence, which prompts people to undergo cosmetic surgery at a rate of 30%.
6. Women under 30 years of age are the least likely to resort to cosmetic surgeries.
7. Appearance and appearance have a significant impact on getting a job opportunity.

Introduction:

In our era, which has witnessed rapid development in the field of technology and social media, interest in the individual's appearance and personal image has increased. As cosmetic surgery is an option that many resort to in order to support their self-confidence and improve their external appearance, and many in our era also seek to keep up with external beauty by all available means, as the extent of the impact of exaggerated cosmetic surgeries on human health is increasingly evident, and many wonder about the importance of this step and the challenges that may result from it. The results of the study indicate that the spread of this phenomenon was represented by cosmetic procedures in filler and botox injections, while the most advanced cosmetic surgeries are rhinoplasty, followed by weight loss surgeries and hair transplantation. Social motives and the aesthetic image of the external appearance ranked first, followed by the economic motive represented by the media marketing of the culture of beauty. As for the most prominent effects, they are the psychological factor represented by enhancing the mental image of the external appearance and compatible with the prevailing culture of beauty, followed by the economic factor,

as the culture of beauty constitutes a large financial burden on consumers and the medical field has been transformed into a commercial field. This research works to explore the impact of exaggerated cosmetic surgeries on individuals and society in general. We will analyze the factors that push people to make such decisions and we will shed light on the medical and psychological challenges that may arise as a result of these operations through this research.

1 - Research problem: - Resorting to cosmetic surgeries is one of the phenomena that has recently become widespread in society. Many women resort to these surgeries, whether they need them or not, to improve their external appearance, even if this poses a danger to their lives. Therefore, it is necessary to stand on the reasons that lead to resorting to cosmetic surgeries and to know the extent of their danger.

2- Research objective:

1. Knowing the extent of the risk of cosmetic surgeries.
2. Knowing the impact of external appearance on self-confidence.
3. The reason for resorting to dangerous cosmetic surgeries.

3-Research hypothesis:

The following hypotheses were relied upon in formulating the research:

Ho: There is no relationship between the extent of the risk of cosmetic surgeries and the decision to resort to dangerous cosmetic surgeries, meaning that the level of awareness of the risks does not affect the decision to resort to cosmetic surgeries.

H1: There is a relationship between the extent of the risk of cosmetic surgeries and the decision to resort to dangerous cosmetic surgeries, meaning that the level of awareness of the risks affects the decision to resort to cosmetic surgeries.

The theoretical aspect

First: Definition of cosmetic surgeries

Cosmetic surgery is the work of anything that improves something in its external appearance by increasing or decreasing it. Some have defined cosmetic surgeries as a surgery performed to improve the appearance of a part of the visible parts of the body or to function it from its difficulties if it is deficient, damaged or deformed.

With this definition, non-surgical cosmetic surgeries appear, such as the use of some medical preparations in treating the skin and beautifying the face with powders and dyes, cutting and decorating hair, and other works intended for beautification and decoration without the intervention of cosmetic surgery.

From here, we can give cosmetic surgeries a general definition and another specific one. By the general definition, we mean the various operations and works intended for beautification and decoration, whether surgical or non-surgical. As for the specific definition, it refers to surgical cosmetic surgeries in the medical fields mostly.

Second: The concept of cosmetic surgeries:

Cosmetic surgeries and plastic surgery: - It is a type of surgical operation performed for medical or cosmetic purposes such as correcting congenital defects and deformities, or restoring skin or body parts exposed to burns or breathing problems in rhinoplasty or solving breast problems in breast or gynecomastia surgeries, body and abdominal liposuction and tightening, and many others.

Third: Types of cosmetic surgeries

There are two types of cosmetic surgeries according to their purpose:

1- Cosmetic surgeries: - They are based on the aesthetic appearance only, such as nose reduction surgeries, skin injections, and breast augmentation. These surgeries have spread very widely in light of the interest in image and external appearance and imitating celebrities. In many cases, young men and women resort to performing these operations due to a lack of self-confidence and dissatisfaction and self-acceptance, but there are also necessary cosmetic surgeries according to the individual's condition.

2- Reconstructive surgeries: These focus on restoring organs to perform their functional and formal function approximately, and the defect is the result of congenital deformities such as the opening of the upper lip of the mouth (cleft lip), and the increase or decrease of fingers and toes. The process of removing organs affected by cancer such as breast cancer is also considered a reconstructive surgery.

Fourth: The positives of cosmetic surgery

1-Many people use cosmetic surgery to improve their appearance, whether it is to tighten sagging skin or remove lines and wrinkles, a little plastic surgery can change the shape of the face.

2-Many people suffer from confidence issues because of their appearance, and with a little plastic surgery, most people are happier with their appearance and more confident in the world around them because of this new look.

3-Studies have shown that people who undergo cosmetic surgery and have high confidence also have better relationships with their partners and with others, and most of them believe that the reason for this is that they are not so concerned about the way people see them and feel less judged.

4-Those who use cosmetic surgery for medical reasons may find that surgery was the solution to their problems, and one of the most common examples is tightening the eyes around the forehead to reduce eye pain and headaches.

Fifth: The negatives of cosmetic surgery

1-High cost: - Cosmetic surgery is one of the highest costs of surgery, and you can end up spending a lot of money if you think about any cosmetic procedure.

2-Opportunity for addiction: - One of the most negatives that everyone who undergoes plastic surgery suffers from is addiction to more plastic surgery, as it greatly affects the mental image of patients, as they begin to discover new problems after each plastic surgery and see that they need it.

3-Poor psychological state: - Sometimes people who resort to plastic surgery build high hopes on results that come unexpectedly or not as they wanted, as the results are not always guaranteed and may not satisfy the patient.

4- The reaction of others: - If the opinions of others are important to you, it may not be appropriate for you to undergo any plastic surgery, especially if the changes are very noticeable, as you will find many negative comments that affect your psychology. This is an annoying fact for some who care about the opinions of others but are stuck in their instinctive feeling about undergoing surgery to improve their appearance.

5-You need time to recover: - This means that your life, immediately after the surgery, has stopped because you need time to recover, so you will not be able to continue your daily life as you usually do.

Sixth: Complications of cosmetic surgeries

Possible complications of any surgical procedure include the following:

- 1-Anesthesia-related complications, including pneumonia, blood clots, and death in rare cases.
- 2-Infection at the wound site, which may worsen scarring and may require additional surgery.
- 3-Fluid accumulation under the skin Minor bleeding that may require another surgical procedure, or severe bleeding that requires a blood transfusion.
- 4-Abnormal scarring due to skin cracking.
- 5-Wound separation, which sometimes requires additional surgical procedures.
- 6-Feeling numbness and tingling resulting from nerve damage, and this feeling may be permanent.

The applied aspect

(Chi-Square test) Chi-square test: -

categorical: It is a statistical test that shows the existence of a relationship between two categorical variables chi adequate test and is used for multiple purposes as well.

Description of the Chi-Square Test: We use Chi-Square tests to find out the significant difference between the observation data and the expected data that the researcher wants to study and analyze.

Frequencies (observed frequencies): - The frequency distribution of the distributions that can be arranged in ascending or descending order Observations

Expected or Theoretical Frequencies: -

It is the number of cases in each cell or category of the classification categories of the studied phenomenon that determines and stipulates the null hypothesis

Chi-Square is generally known as: - A measure of the extent of the disparity between the expected frequency and the observed frequency and the calculation is as follows: -

$$(X^2 = \sum(O_i - E_i) / E \dots)$$

Where: -

Frequencies of observations in the cell: o_i

Expected frequencies in the cell: E_i

Note: - All results were compared at the 0.05 level based on the hypotheses, including:

The values of the first variable are not affected by the values of the second variable: null hypothesis The null hypothesis

It says that there is a relationship between the two variables such that our knowledge of the values of the first: - alternative hypothesis While the alternative theory enables us to predict the second variable.

The data was collected through the form and variables for the Chi-square measure for statistical data using the ready-made application SPSS

The sample was obtained as follows:

Table (1): Marital status * Age.

Crosstab				
Count				
		age		Total
		Less than 30	More than 30	
marital status	married	6	14	20
	Single	25	5	30
Total		31	19	50

Chi-Square Tests					
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	14.488 ^a	1	.000		
Continuity Correction ^b	12.313	1	.000		
Likelihood Ratio	14.938	1	.000		
Fisher's Exact Test				.000	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	14.198	1	.000		
N of Valid Cases	50				

From Table (1) it is clear that the value of Chi-square is equal to (14.488) and the value of sig is (0.00) which is equal to less than the significant value (0.05) and this means the existence of a significant relationship, so we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis.

Ho: There is no significant relationship between marital status and age.

H1: There is a significant relationship between marital status and age.

Table (2): Do you have an idea that there are deaths resulting from cosmetic surgeries? * Bullying has a societal role in pressuring people to undergo cosmetic surgeries.

Crosstab					
Count					
		bullying active role			Total
		Yes	sometimes	No	
You have the vision	Yes	22	6	0	28
	sometimes	8	6	0	14
	No	4	2	2	8
Total		34	14	2	50

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	13.145 ^a	4	.011
Likelihood Ratio	9.890	4	.042

Linear-by-Linear Association	5.845	1	.016
N of Valid Cases	50		

From Table (2), it is clear that the value of Chi-square is equal to (13.145) and the value of sig is (0.01), which is less than the significant value (0.05), which means that there is a significant relationship, so we reject the zero and accept the alternative.

Ho: There is no significant relationship between You have a perception that there are deaths resulting from cosmetic surgeries * Bullying has a societal role in pressuring towards cosmetic surgeries.

H1: There is a significant relationship between You have a perception that there are deaths resulting from cosmetic surgeries * Bullying has a societal role in pressuring towards cosmetic surgeries.

Table (3): Setting controls to limit dangerous cosmetic surgeries * Tightening legal oversight by the government on the cosmetic industry to protect the consumer.

Crosstab					
Count					
		Tightening legal control			Total
		Yes	sometimes	No	
Set controls	Yes	39	1	1	41
	sometimes	4	3	0	7
	No	1	0	1	2
Total		44	4	2	50

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	24.808 ^a	4	.000
Likelihood Ratio	13.242	4	.010
Linear-by-Linear Association	9.977	1	.002
N of Valid Cases	50		

From Table (3) it is clear that the value of Chi-square is equal to (24.808) and the value of sig is (0.00) which is equal to less than the significant value (0.05) and this means that there is a significant relationship, so we reject the zero and accept the alternative.

Ho: There is no significant relationship between the financial status and the financial cost

H1: There is a significant relationship between the financial status and the financial cost

Table (4): You have the perception that there are cases of death resulting from cosmetic surgeries * Social status.

Crosstab				
Count				
		marital status		Total
		married	Single	
You have the vision	Yes	8	20	28

	sometimes	5	9	14
	No	7	1	8
Total		20	30	50

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	9.152 ^a	2	.010
Likelihood Ratio	9.521	2	.009
Linear-by-Linear Association	7.146	1	.008
N of Valid Cases	50		

From Table (4) it is clear that the value of Chi-square is equal to (9.152) and the value of sig is (0.01) which is equal to less than the value of significance (0.05) and this means the existence of a significant relationship, so we reject the zero and accept the alternative.

Ho: There is no significant relationship between your perception that there are cases of death resulting from cosmetic surgeries and the social status.

H1: There is a significant relationship between your perception that there are cases of death resulting from cosmetic surgeries and the social status.

Table (5): Financial status * External appearance has a direct impact on self-confidence, which leads to cosmetic surgery.

Crosstab					
Count					
		Appearance			Total
		Yes	sometimes	No	
Financial status	good	15	7	0	22
	middle	6	10	7	23
	weak	0	4	1	5
Total		21	21	8	50

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	15.917 ^a	4	.003
Likelihood Ratio	20.229	4	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	12.086	1	.001
N of Valid Cases	50		

From Table (5) it is clear that the value of Chi-square is equal to (15.917) and the value of sig is (0.00) which is equal to less than the significance value (0.05) and this means that there is a significant relationship, so we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis.

Ho: There is no significant relationship between the financial status * external appearance has a direct effect on self-confidence which leads to cosmetic surgery.

H1: There is a significant relationship between the financial status * external appearance has a direct effect on self-confidence which leads to cosmetic surgery.

Table (6): Age * Have you ever thought about undergoing plastic surgery?

Crosstab					
Count					
		My thought one day in submission			Total
		Yes	sometimes	No	
Age	Less than 30	22	5	4	31
	More than 30	6	4	9	19
Total		28	9	13	50

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	8.804 ^a	2	.012
Likelihood Ratio	8.896	2	.012
Linear-by-Linear Association	8.626	1	.003
N of Valid Cases	50		

From Table (6) it is clear that the value of Chi-square is equal to (8.804) and the value of sig is (0.01) which is equal to less than the significant value (0.05) and this means that there is a significant relationship, so we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative.

Ho: There is no significant relationship between age * I thought one day to undergo plastic surgery.

H1: There is a significant relationship between age * I thought one day to undergo plastic surgery.

Table (7): The external appearance has a great impact on obtaining a job opportunity * Financial status.

Crosstab					
Count					
		Financial status			Total
		good	middle	weak	
It is considered a great opportunity for work.	Yes	15	9	1	25
	sometimes	6	13	2	21
	No	1	1	2	4
Total		22	23	5	50

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	12.305 ^a	4	.015.
Likelihood Ratio	9.492	4	.050.
Linear-by-Linear Association	7.069	1	.008.
N of Valid Cases	50		

From Table (7) it is clear that the value of Chi-square is equal to (12.305) and the value of sig is (0.01) which is smaller than the significance value (0.05) which means that there is a significant relationship, so we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis.

Ho: There is no significant relationship between the shape and appearance have a significant impact on obtaining a job opportunity * financial status.

H1: There is a significant relationship between the shape and appearance have a significant impact on obtaining a job opportunity * financial status.

Table (8): Age * Consulting a specialist doctor for a cosmetic procedure

Crosstab				
Count				
		Consult a doctor		Total
		Yes	sometimes	
age	Less than 30	28	3	31
	More than 30	18	1	19
Total		46	4	50

Chi-Square Tests					
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	.312 ^a	1	.577		
Continuity Correction ^b	.000	1	.983		
Likelihood Ratio	.330	1	.566		
Fisher's Exact Test				1.000	.507
Linear-by-Linear Association	.306	1	.580		
N of Valid Cases	50				

From Table (8) it is clear that the value of Chi-square is equal to (0.312) and the value of sig is (0.577) which is equal to greater than the significance value (0.05) and this means that there is no significant relationship, so we reject the alternative hypothesis and accept the null hypothesis.

Ho: There is no significant relationship between age and consulting a specialist doctor to perform a cosmetic surgery.

H1: There is a significant relationship between age and consulting a specialist doctor to perform a cosmetic surgery.

Table (9): Social status * Financial status

Crosstab					
Count					
		Financial status			Total
		good	middle	weak	

marital status	married	10	8	2	20
	Single	12	15	3	30
Total		22	23	5	50

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	.534 ^a	2	.766
Likelihood Ratio	.534	2	.765
Linear-by-Linear Association	.277	1	.599
N of Valid Cases	50		

From Table (9) it is clear that the value of Chi-square is equal to (0.534) and the value of sig is (0.765) which is equal to greater than the value of significance (0.05) and this means that there is no significant relationship, so we reject the alternative hypothesis and accept the null hypothesis.

Ho: There is no significant relationship between social status and financial status.

H1: There is a significant relationship between social status and financial status.

Table (10): Financial status * Bullying has a societal role in pressuring towards cosmetic surgeries

Crosstab					
Count					
		bullying active role			Total
		Yes	sometimes	No	
Financial status	good	16	5	1	22
	middle	16	6	1	23
	weak	2	3	0	5
Total		34	14	2	50

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	2.957 ^a	4	.565
Likelihood Ratio	2.816	4	.589
Linear-by-Linear Association	.669	1	.414
N of Valid Cases	50		

From Table (10) it is clear that the value of Chi-square is equal to (2.957) and the value of sig is (0.565) which is equal to greater than the significant value (0.05) which means there is no significant relationship, so we reject the alternative hypothesis and accept the null hypothesis.

Ho: There is no significant relationship between the financial status and bullying has a societal role in pressuring towards cosmetic surgery.

H1: There is a significant relationship between the financial status and bullying has a societal role in pressuring towards cosmetic surgery.

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